

Pressure- and Aggregation-Induced Modulation of Linear and Nonlinear Optical Properties in a Push–Pull Chromophore: Insights from Computational Modelling

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Abstract

We report a theoretical investigation of the structural and optical response of a molecular crystal based on a push-pull chromophore subjected to increasing isotropic pressure. Geometry optimizations at the DFT level reveal pronounced changes in unit cell parameters, particularly along the stacking and charge-transfer directions, accompanied by significant volume compression. Pressure also alters key intramolecular torsional angles and intermolecular stacking geometries, with non-linear variations and discontinuities observed in the evolution of these parameters. Time-dependent DFT calculations on pressure-adapted geometries of molecular dimers show that these

structural changes lead to abrupt shifts in excited-state energies, oscillator strengths, exciton localization, and charge-transfer character. Notably, the second harmonic generation response of the dimers, representative of molecular stacking in thin films, is highly sensitive to pressure. These results suggest that external pressure provides an effective means to modulate the nonlinear optical properties of 2D materials based on these push-pull chromophores.

Introduction

Controlling the optical properties of organic solids based on π -conjugated chromophores through the application of external pressure is crucial for a wide range of advanced applications, including tunable optoelectronic devices, responsive photonic and sensing materials, data storage technologies, and energy-harvesting systems.¹⁻⁶ In this context, mechanochromic and mechanofluorochromic materials, exhibiting changes in absorption and emission properties, respectively, in response to mechanical stimuli such as grinding, pressing, shearing or stretching, have attracted considerable interest.⁷ Recent examples include donor-acceptor type fluorophores such as phenylenevinylene oligomers,^{8,9} triphenylamine¹⁰ derivatives, organoboron complexes,^{11,12} carbazole-based conjugates,¹³ molecular co-crystals,¹⁴ diketopyrrolopyrrole-based materials,¹⁵ as well as pyridylvinylanthracene-based compounds,^{16,17} which exhibit pronounced and reversible mechanoresponsive optical behaviour driven by changes in molecular packing or $\pi - \pi$ interactions.

Going beyond linear optical responses, NLO properties of organic solids can also be tuned by external pressure.¹⁸⁻²² In this context, Roncali and coworkers reported, over a decade ago, the first example of a material exhibiting NLO mechanochromic behaviour, based on a push-pull chromophore.²³ This chromophore features a diphenylamine (DPA) donor unit N-substituted with an oligo-oxyethylene chain, linked via a thienyl (Th) π -conjugated spacer to a dicyanovinyl (DCV) acceptor group (Figure 1b). In the crystalline state, both head-to-tail and face-to-face molecular arrangements were observed. Notably, thin-film interfaces of this

compound, presumed to retain the non-centrosymmetric face-to-face aggregation found in the crystal, were shown to generate a Second Harmonic Generation (SHG) signal under 800 nm laser excitation. The disappearance of this NLO response upon mechanical smearing of the film suggested that SHG originates from ordered crystalline domains, and that mechanical disruption of the local non-centrosymmetric structure leads to extinction of the SHG signal. This interpretation was further supported by thermal annealing experiments: annealing temporarily suppressed the SHG signal, which gradually reappeared after approximately 30 minutes under ambient conditions, indicating a reorganization toward the original molecular packing.

In this work, we present a computational study aimed at providing deeper insight into the role of molecular aggregation and of external mechanical stress on the linear and nonlinear optical responses of this material, hereafter referred to as DPA-Th-DCV. Our computational strategy relies on the combined use of periodic density functional theory (DFT) to model the crystal structure under increasing isotropic pressure (from 1 to 30 kbar) and time-dependent (TD) DFT calculations to evaluate the associated linear and nonlinear optical responses. This approach allows for the rationalization of the evolution of the optical properties based on the impact of an applied mechanical constraint on the geometry and spatial organisation of the molecular units within the crystal. The results demonstrate how fine-tuning of intermolecular interactions through pressure offers a viable strategy for the controlled modulation of the optical properties in this push-pull system.

Computational Methods

Geometry Optimizations and Calculation of Molecular Optical Properties

Geometry optimizations of DPA-Th-DCV conformers were carried out using DFT with the Gaussian 16 program,²⁴ using the CAM-B3LYP²⁵ exchange-correlation functional (XCF)

Figure 1: Top: Scheme of the optimized crystal structure (a), and chemical structure of DPA-Th-DCV (b). Bottom: Molecular dimer (c) extracted from the unit cell for subsequent calculations of the optical properties. The torsion angles θ_1 and θ_2 discussed in the text are also defined. Angles between the planes of the phenyl rings (γ_1) (d) and between the planes of the thiophenyl rings (γ_2) of the two monomers (e).

with the Grimme D3 empirical dispersion correction²⁶ and the 6-311G(d) basis set. Molecular structures were confirmed to be real minima on the potential surface by the subsequent computation of harmonic vibrational frequencies and the absence of imaginary values. The vertical excitation energies and oscillator strengths associated to the low-lying excited states, as well as the components of the first hyperpolarizability tensor, were computed using TD-DFT at the same CAM-B3LYP-D3/6-311G(d) level of approximation. Linear optical properties were calculated both in the gas phase and, to compare with previously reported results,²³ in three solvents of increasing polarities: hexane ($\epsilon_0 = 1.88$), dichloromethane ($\epsilon_0 = 8.93$) and acetonitrile ($\epsilon_0 = 35.69$). Solvation effects were simulated by means of the polarizable continuum model in its integral equation formalism (IEF-PCM).²⁷

Optimization of Crystal Structures

Periodic DFT calculations were performed with the Quantum Espresso (QE) package^{28,29} using the vdW-df2-c09 XCF, which was shown to accurately describe dispersion-bound van der Waals complexes.^{17,30-32} The ultra-soft pseudopotential scheme was employed in all calculations, with pseudopotentials obtained from the standard solid-state pseudopotentials (SSSP) library.³³⁻³⁵ The BFGS quasi-newton algorithm was used with a threshold of 10^{-4} Ry/Bohr³ on all the atomic forces, and 0.05 GPa (0.3×10^{-5} Ry/Bohr) on the largest component of stress tensor when cell relaxation was applied. The bulk calculations were conducted using a regular $1 \times 1 \times 1$ k -point sampling of the first Brillouin zone. After standard testing, kinetic energy cut-offs of 70 Ry for the wave functions and 490 Ry for the augmentation charge density were adopted to achieve stable convergence of forces and stress. Self-consistent-field (SCF) convergence was achieved with a threshold of 10^{-6} Ry on the total energy. The QE calculations were pre- and post-processed using the Atomic Simulation Environment (ASE).³⁶ The Mercury program³⁷ developed by the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre (CCDC), as well as the VESTA program,³⁸ were used for visualization and exploitation purposes. XRD crystal structures were used as starting guess for geometry optimizations, first without any external constraint to assess the reliability of the computational level, and then upon applying increasing isotropic pressures (up to 30 kbar) to monitor the structural deformations induced by the mechanical stress. To eliminate the possibility of falling into a local minimum, optimizations under pressure were also carried out using the structure obtained at the next lower pressure as the initial guess; the resulting geometries were identical to those obtained when starting from the XRD structure. Note that the experimental crystallographic structure contains two acetonitrile molecules per unit cell, which could not be refined experimentally. Including these solvent molecules was essential to achieve convergence. The calculations converged towards the same structure regardless of their initial orientation. Moreover, the acetonitrile molecules have no impact on the optical properties and were not taken into account in the subsequent TD-DFT calculations.

Calculation of Excited States and Optical Properties of Crystalline Aggregates

As the non-centrosymmetric co-facial (or face-to-face) arrangement adopted by the molecules within the crystal was assumed by Roncali and coworkers²³ to provide a good description of the supramolecular organization in thin films, the associated dimers were extracted from the optimized unit cells (Figure 1). Low-lying excited states and second-order NLO responses were then computed at the TD-DFT/CAM-B3LYP-D3/6-311G(d) level on these structures. The local or intermolecular charge transfer character (CT) of the excited states was further analysed with the TheoDOR toolbox, which uses the one-electron transition density matrix to decompose the excitation into different local and CT contributions.³⁹

The first hyperpolarizability components (β_{ijk}) of monomers and dimers extracted from the optimized crystal structures were calculated both in the static limit and the dynamic (frequency dependent) regime of the second harmonic generation, using the experimental incident wavelength of 800 nm.²³ The components and norm of the first hyperpolarizability vector were then calculated as:

$$\beta_i = \frac{1}{3} \sum_j (\beta_{ijj} + \beta_{jij} + \beta_{jji}) \quad (1)$$

$$\beta = \sqrt{(\beta_x^2 + \beta_y^2 + \beta_z^2)} \quad (2)$$

where z is the charge transfer axis of the molecules. The anisotropy of the NLO response was also characterized as the ratio between the longitudinal and transverse components:

$$\alpha_\beta = \frac{|\beta_z|}{\sqrt{\beta_x^2 + \beta_y^2}} \quad (3)$$

Furthermore, the contributions of the low-lying electronic excited states (S_n) to the NLO responses were analyzed using the Sum-Over-States (SOS) expression of the first hyperpo-

larizability.⁴⁰⁻⁴² Although this scheme is known to overestimate hyperpolarizability values, especially truncated implementations, it has the advantage of expressing the NLO responses in terms of spectroscopic quantities, allowing for a qualitative understanding of the NLO properties. According to this formalism, the general expression of the dynamic diagonal component β_{zzz} in the case of the SHG process reads:

$$\beta_{zzz}^{SOS}(-2\omega; \omega, \omega) = 2 \sum_{n \neq 0} \sum_{m \neq 0} \left\{ \frac{\mu_{0n}^z (\mu_{nm}^z - \mu_{00}^z \delta_{nm}) \mu_{m0}^z}{(\Delta E_{0n} - 2\hbar\omega)(\Delta E_{0m} - \hbar\omega)} + \frac{\mu_{0n}^z (\mu_{nm}^z - \mu_{00}^z \delta_{nm}) \mu_{m0}^z}{(\Delta E_{0n} + \hbar\omega)(\Delta E_{0m} - \hbar\omega)} + \frac{\mu_{0n}^z (\mu_{nm}^z - \mu_{00}^z \delta_{nm}) \mu_{m0}^z}{(\Delta E_{0n} + \hbar\omega)(\Delta E_{0m} + 2\hbar\omega)} \right\} \quad (4)$$

where μ_{0n}^z is the z -component of the transition dipole between the ground (S_0) and n^{th} singlet excited state (S_n), μ_{nm}^z the z -component of the transition dipole moment between states S_n and S_m , μ_{00}^z the z -component of the ground state dipole moment, δ_{nm} the Kronecker delta function, and ΔE_{0n} the energy of the $S_0 \rightarrow S_n$ optical transition. For a dynamic NLO process, the denominators also depend on the energy of the incident laser field. For an incident wavelength of 800 nm, $\hbar\omega = 1.55$ eV, while $\hbar\omega = 0$ in the static limit. All quantities involved in equation 4 were calculated at the TD-DFT level with Gaussian16, except the μ_{nm}^z terms, which were obtained using the Multiwfn software.^{43,44} More details on the SOS expressions are provided in the supporting information (Section 5). In the following, all β values are reported in atomic units (1 a.u. of $\beta = 3.63 \times 10^{-42} \text{ m}^4 \text{ V}^{-1} = 3.2063 \times 10^{-53} \text{ C}^3 \text{ m}^3 \text{ J}^{-2} = 8.641 \times 10^{-33} \text{ esu}$), according to the T convention.⁴⁵

Results and Discussion

Molecular Electronic and Optical Properties

As presented in Table S1, DPA-Th-DCV possesses four quasi isoenergetic conformers, with electronic ground-state showing significant charge transfer between the DPA donor and DCV

acceptor, resulting in dipole moment values exceeding 10 D . The charge distributions within the different chemical fragments of the most stable conformer, calculated using the Mulliken and Natural Population Analysis (NPA) approximations, are reported in Figure S1. The π lone pair of the DPA nitrogen is partially delocalized, as indicated by the NPA electron orbital occupancy of 1.759. The π -electron conjugation is also reflected in the near-zero (0.026 Å) Bond Length Alternation (BLA) along the conjugated bridge connecting the donor and acceptor groups. The UV-Vis absorption spectra of DPA-Th-DCV in the gas phase and in different solvents, computed by weighting the spectrum of each stable conformer by its Boltzmann statistical population at room temperature (Table S1), show a first absorption band in the near-UV range and a second, more intense, in the visible domain (Figure S2). The calculated spectra reproduce the overall shapes observed experimentally,²³ and correctly capture the absence of significant solvent effects, although the computed bands are systematically shifted towards higher energies. The $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ absorption band results from a combination of HOMO \rightarrow LUMO and HOMO-1 \rightarrow LUMO ($\pi - \pi^*$) electron excitations, with the former contributing the most (the numerical details are collected in Tables S2-S5). As shown in Figure 2, the HOMO is spread over the whole conjugated part of DPA-Th-DCV, while the LUMO is shifted towards the DCV acceptor, resulting in a significant intramolecular charge transfer (ICT) upon light absorption, as quantified by the large dipole moment variation between the S_0 and S_1 states (Table S6). The electron density variation map (Figure 2) further illustrates the light-induced ICT from the DPA to the DCV group. It also shows that the oligo-oxyethylene chain does not contribute to the ICT, in accordance with the absence of delocalization of the MOs involved in the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition over this part of the molecule.

The static and dynamic components of the first hyperpolarizability vector for each conformer are reported in Table S7. In both cases, the longitudinal contribution β_z , driven primarily by the β_{zzz} tensor component, dominates over the normal components, in agreement with the internal charge transfer pathway being aligned along the z -axis. This dipolar character of the NLO response is further evidenced by the Unit Sphere Representation (USR)⁴⁶

Figure 2: Frontier molecular orbitals of DPA-Th-DCV and electron density variation involved in the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ vertical excitation. Dark (light) blue lobes in the density map are associated with an increase (decrease) in the electronic density. The calculations were performed at the TD-DFT/CAM-B3LYP-D3/6-311G(d) level.

of the β tensor, which provides a visual illustration of the symmetry of the second-order NLO response as a function of the molecular shape (Figure S3). The large difference between the dynamic and static β vectors ($\beta_{dyn}/\beta_{stat} \sim 18$) highlights significant frequency dispersion effects, as expected from the high absorption intensity of the molecule at the second harmonic wavelength (400 nm). Additionally, the anisotropy factor exhibits a strong dependence on the conformer geometry in both regimes, indicating that it is highly sensitive to dynamic geometrical variations. However, such fluctuations are expected to be considerably constrained in the crystalline state.

Impact of Mechanical Strain on the Crystal Structure

The crystal geometry was first optimized without any external constraint. As shown in Table S8, the calculated lattice parameters show only slight differences with the experimental ones, validating the chosen computational level. The lattice parameters were thus computed using the same level of approximation under increasing isotropic pressures (Table S9). Their deviations with respect to the parameters optimized with no external pressure are presented

in Figures 3a and 3b. While the a cell edge remains quasi constant throughout the entire pressure range considered, the lengths of b and c , which are respectively aligned with the stacking axis and the ICT axis of the molecules (see Figure 1), decrease steadily under mechanical stress, resulting in significant volume compression (Figure 3c). The α angle between b and c cell edges decreases by 4.6° from 0 to 30 kbar, while the two other interaxial angles show less significant variation ($< 1^\circ$).

Figure 3: Evolution of the unit cell parameters a , b and c (a), of the interaxial angles (b) and of the unit cell volume (c) with external pressure (% deviation with respect to the parameters optimized without external pressure).

Pressure-induced variations in the geometric characteristics of molecular dimers extracted from the optimized unit cells were also monitored, and are reported in Tables S10 and S11. Figure 4a depicts the evolution with increasing pressure of the stacking angles γ_1 and γ_2 (see their definition in Figure 1). The two angles decrease smoothly up to 9 kbar, indicating that the mean planes of the two monomers become increasingly parallel as the unit cell is compressed by the external mechanical stress. At 10 kbar, both angles drop abruptly (the evolution of γ_2 over the 0-10 kbar pressure range is illustrated in Figure S4). Beyond this point, the evolution of the two angles differ: while γ_1 continues to decrease, γ_2 instead increases steadily with pressure. Another (smaller) discontinuity is observed at high pressure, around 27 kbar. Similar abrupt variations are found in the evolution of the intramolecular torsional angles θ_1 and θ_2 . As discussed in the following sections, these structural changes alter the overall conjugation and the magnitude of the ICT within individual molecular units, thereby modulating both the linear and nonlinear optical responses of the aggregate.

Figure 4: Evolution of the stacking angles γ_1 and γ_2 (a) and of the molecular torsional angles θ_1 (b) and θ_2 (c) with external pressure. See Figure 1 for the definition of the angles.

To further characterize the evolution of intermolecular interactions with pressure, we resorted to the Non-Covalent Interactions (NCI) method.^{47,48} This approach uses the promolecular density $\rho(r)$ for the determination of the reduced density gradient scalar field (RDG, $s(\rho)$), and the sign of the second eigenvalue of the Hessian density matrix (λ_2) to determine the attractive or repulsive nature of the interactions. Moreover, the NCI results can be interpreted semi-quantitatively by calculating the interaction volume (Ω_{NCI}). Figure 5a and 5b show the RDG and a three-dimensional view of the interaction regions between the molecules within the dimer taken at $P = 0$ kbar (see Figure S5 for equivalent representations at higher pressures). As expected, all intermolecular interactions are dominantly of the weak van der Waals type, with the majority occurring between the conjugated backbones of the molecules. The evolution of Ω_{NCI} with pressure (Figure 5c) shows that the volume of NCI interactions progressively increases (up to 25%) as the unit cell is compressed, and reaches a plateau at about 20 kbar.

Impact of Mechanical Strain on the Linear Optical Properties

Figure 6 displays the nature of the first four singlet excited states (S_1 - S_4) of the dimer at zero external pressure, showing the main contributing electronic excitations and the associated molecular orbitals, all of which remain fully localized on individual molecular units. The $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition is computed at 2.71 eV and exhibits a very low oscillator strength

Figure 5: (a) Reduced density gradient $s(\rho)$ versus $\text{sign}(\lambda_2)\rho$ at $P = 0$ kbar, where the colour scheme goes from blue for strong attractive interactions to red for strong repulsive interactions, passing through green for weak van der Waals interactions; (b) NCI regions in the molecular dimer at $P = 0$ kbar; (c) Evolution of the interaction volume Ω_{NCI} with pressure.

($f_{01} = 0.043$), consistent with Kasha’s model for H-aggregates. This transition is primarily composed of HOMO-1 \rightarrow LUMO and HOMO \rightarrow LUMO+1 excitations, indicating its intramolecular character. In contrast, the $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ and $S_0 \rightarrow S_3$ transitions, located at 3.00 eV and 3.06 eV respectively, exhibit high oscillator strengths ($f_{02} = 1.414$ and $f_{03} = 0.797$) and involve a significant HOMO \rightarrow LUMO contribution, suggesting a partial intermolecular charge transfer nature. Finally, the S_4 state at 3.42 eV is a dark ($f_{02} = 0.020$) intermolecular CT state.

The pressure-dependent evolution of the vertical transition energies and oscillator strengths associated with the S_1 - S_4 states is reported in Table S12 and Figure 7. As expected, the discontinuities observed in the evolution of the dihedral angles around 10 and 27 kbar (Figure 4) are reflected in the evolution of the optical properties, with each state being altered differently. The energy and oscillator strength of the (dark) $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition remain nearly constant across the entire pressure range, indicating that this transition is not affected by the structural changes induced by external mechanical strain. At low external pressures (0-9 kbar), the energy of the $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ transition is virtually unchanged while the associated oscillator strength gradually decreases from 1.4 to 1.1. At 10 kbar, both the transition energy

Figure 6: Molecular orbitals and contributions (in %) of the main electronic excitations involved in the first four excited singlet states of the dimer with no external pressure. Only contributions $>10\%$ are reported.

and oscillator strength exhibit a sharp increase, followed by a gradual decline as pressure is further raised. The transition energy towards the S_3 state follows a similar evolution with a discontinuity at 10 kbar. However, opposite to the trend observed for the $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ transition, the intensity of the $S_0 \rightarrow S_3$ transition dramatically drops at 10 kbar, with the oscillator strength decreasing from 1.095 to 0.238. Beyond this point, it fluctuates and eventually vanishes at the highest pressures. Finally, the $S_0 \rightarrow S_4$ transition, which is dark in the absence of external pressure, exhibits a gradual decrease in energy up to the structural discontinuity, after which it remains almost constant. Meanwhile, the corresponding oscillator strength increases from 15 kbar onward, reaching a substantial value of ~ 0.8 at higher pressures.

The results reported in Figure 7 show that, while the structural changes induced by isotropic pressure only have modest impact on the optical properties within the 0-9 kbar

Figure 7: Pressure-dependent evolution of the energies (a) and oscillator strengths (b) associated with the optical transitions towards the four first excited singlet states of the dimer.

range, they significantly alter the singlet state manifold at higher pressures, both in terms of transition energies and absorption intensities. In order to gain a deeper insight into the topology of the excited states, excitations were decomposed into local (intramolecular) and intermolecular CT contributions using the TheoDORE toolbox.³⁹ Electron-hole correlation plots for the S_1 - S_4 excited states of the dimer are displayed in Figure S6, while the pressure-induced evolution of their respective CT character is depicted in Figure 8, together with the associated exciton size (see Tables S13 and S14 for numerical data). The nature of the excited states at key pressures ($P = 0, 10$ and 30 kbar) is further illustrated by the variation of the electron density upon excitation towards the S_1 - S_4 states, as well as the corresponding charge transfer vectors, following the procedure proposed by Le Bahers and coworkers^{49,50} (Figures S7 and S8).

At zero external pressure, the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition is purely local in nature and corresponds to intramolecular excitations on both monomers, as expected from the MO contributions shown in Figure 6. This local character is conserved at all pressures, with the intermolecular CT contribution remaining below 5%. The exciton size of about 5 \AA reflects an intramolecular CT from the donor to the acceptor moiety within the two monomers, as confirmed by the

Figure 8: Pressure-induced evolution of the intermolecular charge transfer character (a) and of the exciton size (b) in the $S_1 \rightarrow S_4$ excited states.

charge transfer vector parallel to the conjugation axis of the molecules. In contrast, the S_2 state displays a partial intermolecular CT character of 37% at zero pressure, and larger exciton size (5.8 Å). The CT character gradually increases to 52%, then abruptly drops to 15% at $P = 10$ kbar, before rising smoothly again to reach 31% at $P = 30$ kbar. Analysis of the electron-hole correlation plots reveals that the CT character of S_2 observed before the structural transition corresponds to a charge transfer from monomer **1** to monomer **2**. In contrast, the exciton becomes more localized on monomer **1** after the discontinuity, as also illustrated by the density variation maps and CT vectors in Figures S7 and S8. The abrupt decrease of the CT character of S_2 at 10 kbar aligns with the decrease of the exciton size from 5.9 to 5.3 Å, as well as with a larger absorption intensity, as indicated by the evolution of the oscillator strength of the $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ transition (Figure 7). The S_3 state evolves symmetrically to S_2 , starting with a dominant CT character (59%) at zero pressure, corresponding to a charge transfer from monomer **1** to monomer **2** with an exciton size of 6.2 Å. This CT character gradually decreases up to the structural transition at 10 kbar, before rising abruptly to reach a quasi-pure CT character (89%), corresponding to a charge transfer from monomer **2** to monomer **1**. Here as well, the abrupt variation of the CT character of S_3 aligns with a sharp increase of the exciton size and decrease of the oscillator strength

associated to the $S_0 \rightarrow S_3$ transition. After 10 kbar, while the CT character of S_3 continues to increase progressively with pressure (reaching 95% at $P = 30$ kbar), a close inspection of the electron-hole correlation plots reveals that S_3 gradually evolves towards a charge resonance state. This is further confirmed by both the density variation map and the central position of the CT vector oriented parallel to the CT axis of the molecules. Finally, S_4 initially exhibits a dominant CT character that gradually decreases with increasing pressure, as the exciton becomes more confined. At zero pressure, the charge transfer occurs from monomer **2** to monomer **1**, and reverses direction at $P = 10$ kbar, after which the transfer occurs from monomer **1** to monomer **2**. Beyond this point, and similarly to S_3 , S_4 progressively evolves into a charge-resonance state.

Impact of Mechanical Strain on the Nonlinear Optical Properties

The significant structural changes shown in the previous section to significantly affect the linear optical properties are also expected to strongly influence the NLO response. The evolution with pressure of the static and dynamic components of the first hyperpolarizability vector of the dimer, along with the anisotropy of the NLO response, are summarized in Tables S15 and S16. As in the monomer (Table S7), the β norm (Equation 2) closely follows that of the β_{zzz} component in both the static and dynamic regimes, confirming that the NLO response is predominantly governed by the diagonal component aligned with the intramolecular charge transfer axis. At $P = 0$, the static β_{zzz} response of the dimer is roughly twice that of the monomer, albeit slightly lower, as expected for a face-to-face molecular arrangement. In contrast, the monomer and dimer dynamic β_{zzz} responses yield $\beta_{zzz}^{dim}/2\beta_{zzz}^{mon} \sim 2.1$, indicating that frequency dispersion effects enhance the NLO response of the aggregated dimer. This enhancement arises from the presence of two highly absorbing excited states, namely S_2 and S_3 , near the second-harmonic wavelength (400 nm, 3.1 eV). As illustrated in Figure 9, the static and dynamic β responses of the dimer display markedly different behaviours under pressure. The static β decreases progressively as pressure increases

and exhibits a sharp discontinuity at 10 kbar, which aligns with the abrupt changes observed in the linear optical properties. Conversely, the dynamic β increases with pressure, reaching a maximum at 9 kbar before decreasing at higher pressures. Notably, the evolution of $\beta(-2\omega; \omega, \omega)$ does not present any clear discontinuity, suggesting that the fine dependence of the SHG response to the nature of the excited states is overridden by frequency dispersion effects. Interestingly, the static anisotropy ratios α_β regularly increase with the pressure, from 25.9 to 43.6, highlighting that the 1D directionality of the NLO response is reinforced by the applied mechanical strain. In contrast, the dynamic anisotropy ratios are lower than the static ones (ranging between 8.7 and 12.1), and display much weaker variations with pressure.

Figure 9: Pressure-induced variation of the static (a) and dynamic (b) values of β and β_{zzz} , as calculated at the TD-DFT/CAM-B3LYP-D3/6-311G(d) level.

The pressure dependence of β_{zzz} can be further interpreted using the SOS formalism (Equation 4). In both regimes, the inclusion of only the first four excited states S_1 - S_4 is sufficient to reach a converged β_{zzz} value, as evidenced in Figure S10. As depicted in Figure 10, although the β_{zzz} values obtained from the SOS formalism are systematically larger than those computed with TD-DFT, both methods display the same pressure-dependent behaviour.

The SOS formalism also enables the decomposition of the total β_{zzz} component into con-

Figure 10: Pressure-induced evolution (in % variation with respect to the value calculated at zero pressure) of the static (a) and dynamic (b) first hyperpolarizability, as calculated at the TD-DFT/CAM-B3LYP-D3/6-311G(d) level and using the SOS scheme including the first four excited states.

tributions from individual excited states, as illustrated in Figure 11. In the static regime, the pressure-induced evolution of the individual state contributions closely mirrors the corresponding changes in their respective oscillator strength. In the dynamic case, however, interpretation of the results is more complex, as the contributions depend both on the intrinsic static response of each state and on frequency-dependent dispersion factors. Among the states considered, S_2 and S_3 provide the largest contributions, owing to their excitation energy ($\Delta E \approx 3.0 - 3.2$ eV across the pressure range) remaining close to resonance with the 3.1 eV second harmonic light (corresponding to $\lambda = 400$ nm), see Figure 7). The contribution from S_3 is initially positive (for $\Delta E < 3.1$ eV, up to ~ 9 kbar), but becomes negative as its excitation energy shifts above the resonance. In contrast, the contribution of S_4 is negligible at low pressures and becomes increasingly negative at higher pressures.

Figure 11: Contribution of states S_1 - S_4 to the static (a) and dynamic (b) β_{zzz} components (a.u.), as calculated using the SOS formalism.

Conclusion

In this study, we report a theoretical investigation aiming at rationalizing how external pressure influences the structure and optical properties of a molecular crystal based on the DPA-Th-DCV push-pull chromophore. Periodic DFT optimizations of the crystal structure under increasing isotropic pressure reveal that the applied mechanical strain leads to substantial changes in the unit cell parameters, particularly along the stacking and charge-transfer axes, resulting in a pronounced volume reduction. Pressure also alters key intramolecular torsional angles that directly modulate π -conjugation within the chromophore, as well as intermolecular stacking angles that define the relative orientation of the molecular planes within the crystal. The evolution of these structural parameters is non monotonic and marked by discontinuities, which are mirrored by abrupt changes in both the energies and oscillator strengths of the low-lying excited states, as calculated on molecular dimers extracted from the optimized crystal structures. Detailed analyses of the first four excited singlets also evidence that pressure-induced structural changes significantly impact the exciton localization and the charge-transfer character of the electronic transitions. Furthermore,

TD-DFT calculations indicate that external pressure strongly influences the second harmonic generation response of the dimers, considered representative of the stacking arrangements in thin films. The pressure-induced variation of their SHG response is closely related to the variation of a few set of low-lying excited states, as rationalized using a truncated sum-over-state approach. Overall, these findings suggest that applying external pressure offers a promising route to finely tune the SHG properties of 2D materials based on these push-pull chromophores. Experimental validation of these theoretical predictions, along with systematic combined theoretical and experimental studies, would be highly valuable for establishing general structure-property relationships and designing new pressure-tunable NLO materials.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts of interest to declare.

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Supporting Information Available

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